

Safeguarding Property Rights: Reforming Case Property Management in Pakistan

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Abstract: *The Justice system in Pakistan remains grappling with an overwhelming case backlog, with over two million cases pending, a significant portion of which stems from inadequacies in Case Property Management, specifically, the handling of seized vehicles. This study thoroughly investigates the procedural realities and institutional constraints in car Supardari the judicial release of vehicles under custody within Pakistan's framework of property rights. We employed a mixed-methods research technique, gathering primary data through structured questionnaires administered to law enforcement officials, judicial officers, and affected vehicle owners. The aim was to assess the efficiency of existing administrative and legal procedures in safeguarding ownership rights and ensuring justice in cases involving seized vehicles. The analysis indicates that, despite the Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC), which provides a well-structured legal foundation for Supardari, its implementation remains inconsistent and inefficient. The key identified obstacles include delayed judicial decisions and processes, weak coordination across institutions, and poor maintenance of seized vehicles. These practical shortcomings lead to financial losses, erode public trust, and undermine confidence in Pakistan's justice system. Finally, the study recommended establishing a digital case property management procedure, improving institutional coordination, and prioritizing the updating of existing storage in district-wise programs for relevant authorities. This includes enhancing transparency and accountability, ensuring the justice system's credibility, and strengthening citizens' property rights.*

Keywords: Rights; Car Supardari; Criminal Justice System; Pakistan; Judicial Governance; Case Property Management; Legal Reform

Introduction

Property rights refer to the expected ability of an economic agent to use an asset (Lueck & Miceli, 2004). Over the past decade, the concept of property rights has undergone an incredible transformation driven—on the one hand, by expanding the scope of products and technologies covered by property rights, and on the other hand, by policy shifts promoting a move towards a globally harmonized standard of regulation and enforcement (Goldsmith, 1995; Braga et al.,

2000; Janjua, & Samad, 2007). Property rights are critical to a functioning economy and contribute to well—designed governance. The efficacy and robustness of property rights distinguish economies that achieve sustained economic development from those that remain trapped in stagnation (Gould & Gruben, 1996; Chang, 2001; Kennedy, 2011; Angeles, 2011). Effective property rights catalyst investments lower risk and increase ownership incentives in an economy (Shavell, 2002; Carruthers & Ariovich, 2004).

Case property rights promote the transparent administration of disputed assets, which strengthens faith in legal systems. When effectively enforced, they enhance private property rights by promoting economic stability, accountability, and confidence among people and governance (Prasad, 2003; Schneider, 2005; Falvey et al., 2006). The defense and upholding of case property rights have become essential to preserving institutional stability and confidence as disputes over land, inheritance, and digital assets increase (Haber et al., 2003; Mwangi et al., 2012; Muehlfeld & Wang, 2022). Despite its importance, most developing countries consistently struggle to establish strong and effective Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs). This gap constrains their ability to fully leverage IPRs for sustainable economic progress and societal development (Mingaleva & Mirskikh, 2013; Itanyi, 2016). Prior literature from around the world has explored a range of complex and interrelated challenges in developing countries that impede the efficacy of IPR, including a lack of technology (Jain, 1996; Alguliyev et al., 2015; Rosenbaum et al., 2017). Lack of Effective Enforcement, Poverty, poor economic infrastructure, and lack of quality research are acknowledged by Itanyi (2018), Adewopo (2012), and Olubiyi et al. (2022).

Pakistan, as a developing country, is a significant case in the debate on property rights, particularly concerning constraints on structural and institutional capacity. Despite constitutional safeguards and legal codes that formally recognize and protect property ownership, the practical enforcement of these rights remains inconsistent and often ineffective. Persistent bureaucratic inefficiency, inconsistent judicial interpretation, and limited institutional capacity continue to obstruct the smooth realization of ownership and transfer rights. These challenges are evident not only in immovable property but also extend to movable assets. One of the leading instances arises in Supardari cases, where disputes concerning the temporary custody or possession of seized vehicles reveal deeper flaws in property rights enforcement and judicial administration. In Pakistan, Article 23 allows all citizens to acquire, possess, and dispose of property, but Article 24 protects against deprivation except "by law" and provides compensation for compulsory acquisition. These are the fundamental guarantees that govern state activity and private ownership (the Constitution of Pakistan)¹. Supardari refers to the temporary possession of property, typically vehicles seized in a criminal case, awarded by a court pending investigation or trial. It does not determine ownership; it simply protects property and evidence while minimizing suffering and depreciation. The power derives from Section 516-A of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898 (CrPC), with corresponding post-trial provisions in Sections 517-520 (UNODC).

¹<http://www.commonlii.org/pk/legis/const/1973/3.html#:~:text=Subject%20to%20such%20qualifications%2C%20if.of%20free%20competition%20therein:%20or>

When and why the court refused the Supardari of property, especially vehicles. Vehicles that were not custom-paid (NCP), smuggled, or seized by customs. According to a strong line of authority, courts lack the power to release such automobiles on Supardari because they are subject to departmental adjudication under the Customs Act of 1969². The Supreme Court (2016) overturned High Court orders that had released NCP vehicles; High Courts have followed this rule. Serious concerns about the identity/tempered chassis or competing claims that require fact-finding: courts may deny, defer, or order manufacturer/forensic verification first (SHC 2023)³.

Pakistan's justice system is burdened by significant delays, with over 2 million cases pending. A key factor contributing to this backlog is Case Property Management, especially for seized vehicles. Especially, in Peshawar, 1119 seized vehicles were parked in the main warehouse, where a substantial number was recorded in Daudzai police station, and 36 were accounted in Mathra Police station⁴. Despite legal provisions such as Supardari for interim release, outdated procedures and documentation issues lead to prolonged delays. These delays disproportionately harm ordinary citizens, particularly low-income individuals who rely on their vehicles for income or daily needs. When vehicles are left to deteriorate under the open sky or are misused by authorities, it not only causes financial hardship but also violates property rights and erodes public trust in the justice system.

The objective of this study is threefold: to critically examine the existing legal framework of case property rights in Pakistan, with a specific focus on car Supardari under Sections 516-A, 517, and 523 of the Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC), and assess its adequacy in protecting constitutional rights to property (Articles 23–24). Secondly, examine inconsistencies in judicial practice concerning Supardari cases by analyzing case law and recent judgments to understand why similar circumstances yield divergent court decisions. Third, to capture the lived experiences of affected vehicle owners, focusing on economic losses, depreciation, and misuse of vehicles held in police custody, based on primary data collected through structured questionnaires. To achieve these objectives, we compiled documents on the perspective of legal professionals—including lawyers, judges, and lawmakers—on procedural delays, accountability gaps, and the pressing need for standardized judicial guidelines in Supardari proceedings.

This study makes three important contributions to existing literature on case property rights in Pakistan. First, to review the existing legal framework of case property rights in Pakistan, with a focus on the Car Supardari. Secondly, we collected qualitative data through structured questionnaires from the Police, lawyers, affected persons, and the community. The significance of this study lies in its potential to contribute to broader reforms that strengthen transparency, accountability, and good governance within Pakistan's judicial and administrative systems. By revealing inconsistencies in judicial practice and highlighting the socio-economic consequences of procedural inefficiencies, the research underscores the urgent need for systemic reforms that promote fairness and integrity in legal processes. In doing so, it advances

² <https://www.dawn.com/news/1268100?m>

³ <https://caselaw.shc.gov.pk/caselaw/view-file/MjA2MDQxY2Ztcy1kYzgz?uTm>

⁴ <https://www.dawn.com/news/1916843/1155-seized-vehicles-parked-in-peshawar-police-warehouses-sc-told>

the principle that a just and equitable society—where individual freedoms are protected, and equal opportunities prevail can only thrive under institutions that embody these values. The study's recommendations aim to inform policy measures to curb corruption, enhance institutional accountability, and establish governance frameworks that uphold human dignity and foster an environment conducive to free enterprise.

2. Literature review

2.1. Literature from developed regions

Property rights are critical to a functioning economy and fair governance. When regulations are well-defined and effectively implemented, individuals invest with confidence, and disagreements decrease. In practice, however, law, customs, and ineffective administration can collide, particularly in cases involving seized automobiles. Supardari allows courts to return interim custody to the likely owner while a case is pending, preventing the car from depreciating in value. Judges emphasize that this is not a transfer of ownership, but rather a cautious, conditional arrangement (bond, no sale, produce on demand) designed to protect evidence and justice. According to the literature, courts continually balance two goals: protecting property owners' rights and maintaining the integrity of the case. In short, Supardari aligns with a due process framework that ensures justice is served efficiently while safeguarding property rights. Property rights are crucial to legal systems and economic prosperity, but their scope and enforcement vary significantly across jurisdictions. Sprankling (2014) notes That Treaties and customary international law provide support for the emerging global right to property, despite ongoing contradictions between private ownership and public interest. International law protects private property while permitting regulation in the public interest. ICJ cases (Barcelona Traction; Certain Iranian Assets) emphasize that even when nations regulate, they must treat foreign owners fairly and, where appropriate, offer compensation (Ouellet, 2025; Parlett, 2011).

At the regional level, the European Court of Human Rights emphasized proportionality and judicial control in property disputes (Van der Walt, 2011). In many post-Soviet countries, diverse and fragmented legal norms make it difficult for individuals to feel confident about their property ownership (Åslund, 2013). Social norms also play a role: in Nigeria, customary practices continue to limit many women's property rights, despite the constitution's explicit prohibition (CIPE, 2025; Aluko & Amidu, 2006). Both abuses and solutions are demonstrated in country case studies. The long-standing prohibition on the purchase and sale of farmland in Ukraine has been referred to as one of the most significant abuses of property rights in Europe (Zablotskyy, 2017). Similarly, Nepal's tenure systems illustrate how access to property is intertwined with broader struggles for fairness (Pradhan, 2017). Japan's post-war reforms are a textbook case of secure tenure powering recovery and broad-based growth (Watase, 2017). South Africa's land-title programs highlight property rights as a practical tool for empowerment amid long-standing inequality (Wellman & Urbach, 2017; Cousins, 2016). Secure property rights are closely linked to investment, effective land use, and long-term growth, according to economists (Besley & Ghatak, 2010; [Recent land-use research, 2024]). The idea of property has expanded beyond land to include intellectual and cultural spheres. Indigenous Australians, for instance, have protected their traditional arts through copyright and

trademarks, although there remain significant gaps in protection for oral traditions (WIPO, 2017; Anderson, 2009).

2.2. Literature from developing regions

In many developing countries, the handling of property seized in criminal or administrative actions reveals fundamental institutional strengths and flaws. A notable example is the management of motor vehicles in police custody: once seized, vehicles are typically detained for extended periods, resulting in rapid degradation and loss of utility. To reduce welfare and efficiency costs while preserving evidentiary value, courts throughout South Asia use *Supardari* (interim-custody) orders, which return provisional possession to the ostensible owner or a court-approved custodian under bond and non-alienation conditions, pending final adjudication. In effect, courts are balancing two goals: preserving the vehicle's probative value and ensuring the owner's constitutionally protected property and livelihood interests (Sunderbhai Ambalal Desai v. State of Gujarat, 2002; Bardhan, 1989). The *Supardari* system also highlights broader issues in developing nations, where legal property rights are unstable, and enforcement authorities are overburdened. De Soto (2000) notably stated that insecure or informal rights imprison wealth in "dead capital," which prevents assets from contributing to economic progress. In instances of seized vehicles, delayed or ambiguous judicial rulings not only hurt people by reducing their income and mobility but also destroy public trust in the legal system. Scholars have noted that such arrangements approximate caretaker property systems found in agricultural communities, in which property is held in trust until conflicts are resolved (Platteau, 2000). While rationally, these procedures can reinforce inequities, especially when women and other groups do not have equal access to court processes (Agarwal, 1994).

License suspension reduces recurrence and collision rates among DWI (Driving While Intoxicated) offenders, but up to 75% continue to drive illegally. States have enacted automobile impoundment or immobilization legislation for repeat offenders; however, enforcement is rare, and evaluations are often inadequate (Voas & DeYoung, 2002). Driving while suspended, especially among those convicted of impaired driving charges, poses substantial highway safety dangers, with such drivers four times more likely to be involved in fatal crashes with a BAC of more than 0.10. Research in Hamilton County, Ohio, found that impounding rather than immobilizing vehicles resulted in a significant reduction in recurrent DUI charges among numerous offenders, similar to prior findings from Franklin County, where vehicle immobilization was used (Voas et al., 1998). Watson et al. (2020) examined data from Victoria (2006-2014) and focused on 17,440 eligible offenses, of which 41.8% resulted in impoundment. The findings show that the impounded drivers were mainly male and younger, and held probationary licenses. Importantly, re-offense rates were significantly lower for those whose vehicles were detained than for those whose vehicles were not, suggesting a reduction in speeding behavior during the impoundment period, with a more substantial effect on license suspension rates. These findings indicate that vehicle impoundment could help reduce dangerous driving behaviors.

Nwagwu et al. (2020) Report That Road safety management changes in Nigeria aim to control operations, minimize accidents, and improve safety. The Federal Road Safety Corps oversees the implementation of these improvements, spurred by rising accident rates. This study examined the effectiveness of road safety education and the Corps' institutional capacity

in the Southeast. Using mixed methods and a structural-functional approach, the findings revealed difficulties in achieving objectives due to poor implementation and a lack of institutional support, thereby lowering road safety standards.

The South Asian experience illustrates this duality vividly. In Pakistan and India, Supardari orders are commonly invoked to prevent unnecessary loss of value in vehicles, yet procedural ambiguities often prolong disputes and reinforce dependence on judicial discretion (Bardhan, 1989; Agarwal, 1994). In Nepal, Pradhan (2017) shows that customary caretaker norms continue to shape rural land tenure, creating tensions with statutory property laws. These parallels reveal that Supardari is not an isolated practice but rather part of a wider Asian reality in which statutory, customary, and religious systems intersect to shape property relations (Alden Wily, 2012; Sprankling, 2014).

2.3. Property Rights in Pakistan: constitutional and statutory framework

In Pakistan, property rights rest on constitutional guarantees and a long-standing statutory regime: Article 23 secures every citizen's right to acquire, hold, and dispose of property, while Article 24 bars compulsory acquisition except by law, for a public purpose, and with compensation; Articles 172–173 vest ownerless property and key natural resources in the state and authorize the Federation and Provinces to acquire, hold, and dispose of property in their own names. Statutorily, the system distinguishes immovable property (land/buildings; with exclusions such as standing timber, crops, and grass) from movable property (e.g., vehicles), with title and private transactions governed chiefly by the Transfer of Property Act, 1882, the Registration Act, 1908, and revenue laws (e.g., the Land Revenue Act, 1967 and provincial variants) that regulate conveyance, registration, mutation, and record-keeping. Administration lies primarily with provincial revenue departments and the civil courts, with registration serving as the core public-notice mechanism to enhance certainty and reduce disputes. Recent reforms—most notably the Punjab Land Records Authority Act, 2017 and allied digitization initiatives—aim to improve accuracy, access, and service delivery, but implementation gaps persist (dual manual–digital systems, slow dispute resolution, and unequal access, particularly for women). Policy priorities include completing digital cadastral records, standardizing services across provinces, expediting title adjudication, and embedding gender-responsive measures, all while upholding the Constitution's protections.

2.4. Critical Review of Literature and Literature Gap

Despite scattered case law, there is no comprehensive, Pakistan-focused study that systematically examines how the concept of Supardari is applied across courts; yet, practice reveals significant gaps between the law and its implementation. Although Section 516-A Cr.P.C. empowers courts to grant interim custody, vehicles are routinely kept in malkhanas for long periods despite clear ownership, thereby depreciating in value. At the same time, owners face costly delays and procedural hurdles (Arif Ullah v. The State, IHC, 2022). Appellate practice is fragmented: High Courts have issued divergent orders on similar facts—some directing prompt release on Supardari, while others refuse relief even where the title is uncontested—producing jurisdiction-by-jurisdiction uncertainty (e.g., the recent Sindh High Court Supardari decision, March 2024). In the Peshawar High Court, additional burdens—such as extensive documentation or proof of non-collusion at the preliminary stage—further frustrate owners (Biradar Khan). Taken together, weak implementation, inconsistent standards,

and procedural overreach undermine the protective intent of the Cr.P.C., exposing vehicle owners to prolonged litigation, financial loss, and legal uncertainty despite having statutory recourse. This study addresses that gap by providing the first structured analysis of Pakistan's car Supardari regime, its cross-court inconsistencies, and the reforms needed to restore predictability and protect property rights.

3. Research methodology

The law of Supardari, which governs the temporary custody of case property, such as vehicles seized during investigations, affects thousands of citizens across Pakistan every year. Despite being well-embedded in the Criminal Procedure Code, its application remains inconsistent and at times arbitrary, leaving car owners, officials, and even courts themselves in a web of uncertainty. Vehicles often rust away in malkhanas (police storerooms), owners spend years pursuing custody, and police or excise authorities are burdened with safeguarding property they neither own nor benefit from. This study takes a people-centered approach, recognizing that laws are not just abstract rules but living realities that shape livelihoods and trust in the justice system. By directly engaging with lawyers, judges, magistrates, police officials, excise officers, civil society members, and individuals who have personally experienced the Supardari process, the research seeks to uncover how the system actually operates, where it fails, and how it might be reformed to serve justice more effectively.

3.1. Research Design

This is a qualitative, exploratory study, primarily based on field data. While court judgments and legal texts provide important background, they often tell us only part of the story. To capture the lived realities of how Supardari works in practice, the research relies on primary data collected from legal professionals, enforcement agencies, judicial officers, civil society, and directly affected individuals. The design draws inspiration from law-and-society scholarship, where primary surveys and descriptive analyses are used to bridge the gap between law "in the books" and law "in action" (Hirsch & Lazarus-Black, 1994; Merry, 1990). It also follows the tradition of applied legal research in Pakistan, where scholars increasingly emphasize field-based inquiry into judicial practices (Rehman & Sulaiman, 2025).

3.2. Population and Sampling Strategy

The study population was defined to reflect the whole ecosystem of case property management. Respondents were drawn from six stakeholder groups:

- Practicing lawyers in criminal and property law.
- Police officials
- Excise & taxation officials (Current, Retired).
- Judicial actors (Magistrates and Retired judges).
- Civil society Representatives (activists, journalists, community leaders).
- Affected individuals whose cars were seized as case property.

3.3. Data Collection

Data was gathered through structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews.

- The questionnaire captured demographic profiles, professional exposure to Supardari cases, perceptions of fairness, delays, and financial or social costs.

- Semi-structured interviews encouraged respondents to narrate their personal experiences, whether as advocates defending a client, magistrates deciding custody, or owners fighting for the return of their vehicle.

The tools were digitized using Microsoft Forms to streamline collection and reduce errors. A pilot test was conducted with a short sample of lawyers, magistrates, and police officials in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Feedback from the pilot led to the addition of questions on car depreciation in Malkhanas and judicial inconsistencies.

3.4. Analytical Framework

The study employed descriptive analysis as its primary method. This approach is well-suited for studies that aim to document and interpret real-world experiences without imposing restrictive models (Neuman, 2014). Descriptive statistics, percentages, frequency distributions, and cross-tabulations were used to summarize questionnaire responses, including the proportion of owners reporting financial losses and the share of lawyers acknowledging judicial inconsistency in Supardari decisions. By combining descriptive analysis with qualitative narratives, the study maintains both breadth and depth, enriching statistical trends with human stories.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Lawyer perceptions about Vehicles Supardari

To ensure the reliability of the findings, the perception study primarily drew on insights from practicing lawyers and senior members of district and high-court bar associations, most of whom had extensive experience in criminal and property-related cases. To ensure the reliability of their perspectives, a small group of retired judges and magistrates was also interviewed to cross-check the findings. However, no clear evidence emerged indicating that the general public is adequately informed about the legal procedures governing vehicle custody (Supardari) or broader property rights in cases. This gap highlights the limited public awareness and accessibility of information within the legal system.

Figure 1: High Legal Literacy, Low Public Reach

The figures highlight a strong contrast between legal practitioners' awareness of constitutional protections and the general public's understanding of vehicle Supardari laws. While a significant majority of lawyers (92%) reported being fully aware of the relevant

constitutional provisions and sections of the Criminal Procedure Code (sections 516-A, 517, and 523), public awareness appears limited. Nearly 69% of respondents indicated that people are not informed about vehicle seizure procedures or property rights. This suggests that, although legal professionals possess substantial knowledge of constitutional safeguards, this awareness has not effectively translated into public understanding. The data highlights a critical communication and outreach gap between the justice system and ordinary citizens, particularly regarding rights associated with confiscated or seized property.

Figure 2: Speed Without Standardization: Assessing Supardari Decision Practice in Pakistan

Figure 2 points to a system that is fast but uneven. A slight majority, 53 percent, say courts follow a consistent procedure in Supardari matters, while 39 percent experience consistency only some of the time, and 8 percent report that it is rare. On timeliness, the picture is stronger: 84 percent say decisions are reached in less than one month, 8 percent in a one- to three-month window, and another 8 percent in a three- to six-month window. Practitioners often report that cases typically take longer than the stated timelines. Delays come from file shuffling, missing documents, scheduling backlogs, and differences across districts. Weak enforcement of seized-vehicle SOPs (chain of custody, condition checks, secure storage) leads to misuse in custody, undermining trust and complicating Supardari.

Table 1: Misuse Despite SOPs and Reporting Tools

Question	Responses	Percentage/Perceptions
Are SOPs for Car Seized/Supardari in place?	Yes	100%
How often are seized vehicles misused in police custody?	Frequently	77%
	Rarely	23%
Should there be a mandatory reporting system (mailing, condition photos, usage logs)	Yes quarterly	62%
	No	22%
	Monthly	8%
	Yes annually	8%

Source: Author's own tabulation

Respondents unanimously confirm that standard operating procedures for seized vehicles are already in place. However, misuse remains widespread: about 77 percent say vehicles are frequently misused in police custody, while only 23 percent consider such misuse rare. To close this gap, most respondents want reporting to be mandatory and routine, with roughly 62% preferring a quarterly cadence, 8% favoring monthly updates, and another 8% opting for annual reports; about 23% would not require reporting. In short, the problem is not the absence of rules but weak enforcement and transparency. SOPs exist, but without a firm reporting regime and oversight, vehicles continue to be misused. Crucially, misuse of vehicles under Supardari does not occur in a vacuum.

Figure 3: From SOPs to Reality: Delay, Deterioration, and Cost

Building on the earlier finding that SOPs exist but misuse persists, Figure 3 illustrates how enforcement gaps translate into hardship and increased costs, particularly for low-income claimants. The results show a mixed experience for claimants. First, on balance between rights and hardship, 46% feel current practice protects rights, 31% say it creates hardship, and 23% report that both co-occur. Next, regarding case disposition after investigations, most respondents indicate that vehicles are returned to owners on Supardari (85%), while 15% say vehicles are retained until the trial concludes. Finally, on who should bear the storage and maintenance costs during custody, opinions split evenly: 46% point to the government treasury, 46% to the police department, and only 8% assign costs to the owner after release. The results indicate that the sequence points to rules on paper but uneven compliance in practice, leading to delays, deterioration, and additional expenses that fall hardest on low-income applicants.

Table 2: Public awareness of car Supardari and auctions

Question	Responses	Percentage/ Perceptions
Do you find the current auction system transparent and fair	Not Sure	8%
	No	46%
	Yes	46%
Non-Custom and Illegal Imports of Vehicles	Owner with a chance to make it legal	8%

	Auction by FBR/customs	39%
	Return to bona fide purchaser	54%
Public awareness about car Supardari and Auction	No	46%
	Yes	54%

Source: Author's own tabulation

The results present a mixed picture regarding knowledge and fairness. Public awareness of car Supardari and auctions is mixed: 54% say people are aware, while 46% say they are not. For non-custom or illegally imported vehicles, most respondents favor returning the asset to a bona fide purchaser (54%), while 39% support an auction by the revenue and customs authorities, and 8% would allow the current possessor to regularize the vehicle. Opinions on the fairness of the auction system are evenly split: 46% say it is transparent and fair, 46% disagree, and 8% are unsure. People are often unclear about their rights, results vary widely, and trust in the auction process is low. The fix: clear public guidance, strict pre-auction checks, and fully transparent, auditable auctions.

4.2. Administrative Authorities

The Police and Excise departments are the primary authorities responsible for managing car Supardari (the release of seized vehicles). The police handle the initial seizure, custody, and submission of case records to the court, while the Excise Department oversees verification of vehicle registration, ownership, and taxation before release. Their coordinated role ensures that vehicles are lawfully held, verified, and returned under judicial supervision, maintaining both administrative accountability and legal compliance.

Figure 4: Administrative Involvement and Legal Provisions Governing Vehicle Supardari

a) Police and Excise direct Involvement in a vehicle Supardari

b) Law or Section for the vehicle Supardari

The results highlight clear administrative patterns and legal references in vehicle Supardari processes. A majority (63%) noted that the administrative Departments (police and Excise) are directly involved in Supardari, reflecting the operational role of police and allied

agencies in managing vehicle custody and court coordination. This level of engagement suggests that administrative oversight is strong but could benefit from standardized inter-departmental coordination mechanisms. When asked about reforms to improve judicial and administrative efficiency, 63% rated them very important, 25% important, and 13% somewhat important. This consensus underscores a strong institutional demand for procedural clarity, reduced case delays, and the digitization of custody management systems. Regarding vehicle Supardari within the legal framework, 63% cited the Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC, Sections 516-A, 517, 523) as the principal legal basis for vehicle custody decisions, followed by 25% citing the Motor Vehicle Ordinance/Excise Laws and 13% citing the Customs Act, 1969. These findings show that CrPC provisions dominate current administrative practice, while overlapping laws like the Excise and Customs Acts may still create procedural ambiguity, reinforcing the need for a unified legal interpretation and clearer operational SOPs

Table 3: Alignment Between Legal Overlap Perceptions and Process Clarity

Indicator	Response breakdown	Result
Overlapping of different laws	Yes	50%
	No	50%
Clarity of the process for legal provisions on vehicle handling	Yes	74%
	Not sure	13%
	No	13%

The results show that half of the respondents report overlapping laws, while the other half do not, revealing a split understanding of how different statutes apply in Supardari contexts. At the same time, most respondents find the operational process clear in practice, with 74 percent indicating agreement and only 26 percent expressing uncertainty or a negative view.

Overall, the pattern suggests that frontline procedures are generally understood, even as the underlying legal framework feels fragmented. This points to a practical path forward: preserve the workable SOPs that deliver clarity on the ground, while issuing a simple consolidation note that maps CrPC, Motor Vehicle, and Excise provisions to specific steps in the process to reduce perceived overlap.

Figure 5: Custody Duration, Record Systems, and Maintenance of Seized Vehicles

a) Vehicle in Custody

b) Car storage and Protection System

The data in Figure (a) shows that vehicle custody often extends well beyond a reasonable period. A total of 76% of vehicles remain impounded for up to one year, 38% for less than six months, and another 38% for six to twelve months, while 26% stay longer than a year, with 13% held for one to two years and another 13% for more than two years. These findings reinforce earlier results, which showed weak record-keeping and unclear timelines. The results in Figure B reveal critical operational gaps in the management and maintenance of seized vehicles during custody. Half of the respondents (50%) reported maintaining only partial records, using a combination of manual and digital methods. In comparison, 38% indicated a comprehensive digital system, and 13% stated that no records are kept. This inconsistency in documentation weakens accountability and supports earlier findings that unclear procedures and overlapping laws contribute to prolonged custody. Maintenance practices show a similar pattern: only 50% conduct regular condition checks, while 25% do so occasionally and 25% not at all, which helps explain why 80% of respondents earlier linked extended custody to depreciation and loss. On the financial side, 38% stated there is no system in place to cover the cost of vehicle storage; another 25% said no such storage system exists; and 25% rely on the department budget. Only 13% recover costs through court orders. These gaps reinforce earlier results that call for digital inventory systems, defined cost frameworks, and time-bound judicial decisions to prevent unnecessary vehicle deterioration and improve administrative efficiency in Supardari cases.

Figure 4: Accountability, Transparency, and Misuse Prevention in Vehicle Custody Management

Question	Responses	Percentage/ Perceptions
Complaint against the seized car used by the government officials	Frequently	38%
	Never	25%
	Rarely	25%
	Occasionally	13%
Reporting Mandatory Record of custody vehicle	No	13%
	Yes, annually	25%
	Yes, quarterly	63%
System Accountability	No	38%
	Yes	63%

Source: Author's own tabulation

The data in the table above reveal recurring concerns about the misuse of seized vehicles. The results point to a clear policy–practice gap. A slight majority (51%) report complaints about officials using seized cars at least occasionally. 38% say seized cars were used frequently by officials, with another 13% reporting occasional use; 25% say it happened rarely, and 25% say it never happened. Most respondents believe there should be a mandatory record—63% report that a quarterly reporting system is in place, 25% say an annual system is required, and 13% indicate no requirement—yet there is no public, centralized dashboard. Regarding accountability, 63% believe mechanisms exist, while 38% say there is no such mechanism or system available. Together, these figures demonstrate rules on paper but weak transparency and uneven enforcement, highlighting the need for uniform quarterly reporting,

independent oversight, and a public-facing portal to track seizures, releases, and Supardari. Instituting a unified digital record with automatic quarterly reporting would strengthen transparency, reduce misuse, and align with calls for reform for clear timelines and custodial responsibility across departments.

Figure 6: Standard Guideline for car custody

The results show that a large majority, 88%, report having standard guidelines for handling vehicles in custody, while 12% indicate none exist. This suggests that formal procedures for managing seized vehicles are established mainly; however, the slight gap indicates inconsistency in enforcement or awareness.

Strengthening the application and monitoring of these guidelines can help ensure transparency, protect vehicle condition, and support timely release to rightful owners.

Figure 7: Vehicles Auction processes and Data details

a) Vehicle Auction Processes

b) Data Details

The results show two equally used disposal channels: half say auctions go through FBR/Customs, and half say other routes, which signals non-uniform practice across agencies. After investigation, most cases end with the vehicle being returned to the owner through Supardari (63%). In comparison, smaller portions are either kept until the trial ends (13%), released or disposed of by a specific court order (13%), or auctioned by the department or state (13%). Views on auction oversight are mixed but generally positive: 63% consider the process transparent and accountable, yet 25% are unsure, and 13% disagree. Overall, the system generally favors release to rightful owners; however, disposal pathways are split across various channels, and confidence in auction oversight is only moderate. Despite half of the respondents believing that data are available, no public portal or dashboard reports the numbers of vehicles seized, released, or placed on Supardari on a year-by-year basis. Authorities corroborate this view: roughly half confirm that no central system exists, and 38% note that while some records

may exist, they are neither consolidated nor publicly accessible. This perception–reality gap underscores the need for a transparent and regularly updated public reporting platform.

4.3. Perception of the affected Persons

Vehicles serve as a primary source of income for many citizens, particularly those engaged in transport, delivery, and daily commuting work. However, when police or other enforcement authorities seize these vehicles, they often remain in custody for extended periods without a clear or uniform legal framework governing their handling and release. This survey seeks to understand current practices, challenges, and professional perspectives to help improve transparency, accountability, and timeliness in vehicle Supardari (interim release) procedures.

Figure 8: Main source of income, Affected person's income, and vehicle

a) Main source of income

b) Type of Vehicle and income of the affected persons

The data in Figures a and b shows that vehicles play a vital role in income generation for most affected individuals. As shown in Figure a, 75% of respondents reported that their vehicles were their primary source of income, typically used for taxi, delivery, or transport-related work. In comparison, only 25% said they were not dependent on their vehicle for livelihood. Figure (b) further supports this by showing that 100% of the seized vehicles were cars, primarily linked to lower and middle-income groups. Among respondents, 50% reported monthly household incomes between PKR 50,001 and PKR 100,000, 25% reported incomes between PKR 25,000 and PKR 50,000, and 13% reported incomes less than PKR 25,000. These results indicate that vehicle seizures disproportionately affect individuals who rely on their cars for daily income, often from modest-income households.

Table 5: Economic and social impact of vehicle seizure on affected individuals

Question	Responses	Percentage/ Perceptions
How the seizure of your vehicle affected your income	lost a significant share of income	75%
	Completely lost source of income	13%

	Reduced income somewhat	13%
borrow money or sell assets to manage expenses	Yes	88%
	No	13%
Has your household faced difficulty in meeting basic needs (food)	Yes, somewhat	88%
	No	13%

The results in Figure 2 show the economic and social impact of vehicle seizure on affected individuals. A large majority, 75%, reported losing a significant share of their income, while smaller proportions — 12.5% each — either completely lost their income or experienced somewhat reduced earnings. Financial strain is further reflected in coping responses, as 87.5% reported having to borrow money or sell assets to manage household expenses. The same proportion, 87.5%, also reported difficulty meeting basic needs such as food, highlighting how deeply vehicle custody disrupts livelihoods. These findings reinforce that vehicle seizure directly undermines financial stability and worsens vulnerability among already low- to middle-income groups. This is because of the unnecessary seizure and long-term custody by the police and the responsible authorities.

Figure 9: Car in Custody

The results show that prolonged police vehicle custody is common and financially damaging. About 37.5% report holding assets for under six months, 25% for more than two years, and 12.5% each fall within the six to twelve months, one to two years, or less than a year ranges. Because many households rely on these vehicles for their daily income, long and often unnecessary detentions directly cut earnings and heighten financial stress. In short, extended custody periods translate into real income losses for affected owners.

Furthermore, Owners were not adequately informed about the location, status, or condition of their vehicles while in custody, and communication regarding maintenance or costs was unclear.

Table 6: Information and Oversight Gaps in Vehicle Custody

Question	Responses	Percentage/ Perceptions
Notice about the condition and custody.	Sometime	25%
	never	75%
Notice about damage or misuse.	Maybe	13%
	No	13%
	Yes	75%

The data show that most owners were not kept informed about their vehicle’s condition or custody status. 75% said they never received any updates, while only 25% were sometimes informed. Likewise, 75% of respondents reported noticing damage or misuse of their vehicles while in custody, compared to 13% who said “no” and another 13% who were uncertain. Based on the results, several affected persons later noticed damage or suspected misuse while the vehicles were in custody, highlighting gaps in transparency and oversight. These results highlight weaknesses in communication and monitoring systems, leading to mistrust and potentially resulting in the mishandling of seized vehicles. The custody regime exhibits a clear gap in the implementation of rights. Inadequate notification about location, condition, and handling during custody undermines owners’ procedural rights to information and oversight. At the same time, post-custody reports of damage or misuse indicate weak chain-of-custody controls.

Figure 10: Rights, Inspection, and Accountability in Vehicle Custody

The figure highlights significant gaps in rights protection and accountability during vehicle custody. Most respondents indicated that their rights were not protected, and they believed they should have the right to inspect their vehicles while in custody. The majority assigned responsibility for vehicle safety and the prevention of misuse to the judiciary, followed by the police and the government. This suggests that people view vehicle custody not only as a procedural issue but also as a matter of rights and institutional responsibility, underscoring the need for precise oversight mechanisms and transparent access for vehicle owners.

4.4. Community responses

Car Supardari in Pakistan refers to the interim return of a seized vehicle to its lawful claimant. At the same time, a criminal or administrative case remains pending, typically ordered by a magistrate under Section 516-A of the Code of Criminal Procedure and related police standing orders. In practice, it balances preservation of evidence with the owner’s right to use an essential asset, usually against a surety bond and conditions on sale or transfer. Implementation is uneven, with delays in verification, record mismatches, storage losses, and discretion at the thana and court level that can raise transaction costs for citizens. Low public

awareness of procedures and required documents exacerbates hardship, particularly for low-income households that rely on vehicles for their daily income.

Figure 11: Public Knowledge and Awareness of Car Supardari and Vehicle Seizure Rights in Pakistan

The results show a tight sequence from low knowledge to low trust and mixed satisfaction. Only 25% of respondents fully understand the Supardari process (with 35% somewhat aware and 40% not at all), so three in four lack complete procedural literacy. This knowledge gap aligns with perceptions of vehicle safety in custody: 45% say vehicles are often misused, 25% sometimes misused, 25% are well-protected, and 5% suspect misuse by officials, yielding a net perception of misuse of 70% versus 25% positive. These views contribute to the overall opinion of car Supardari in police custody, with 45% dissatisfied, 30% satisfied, and 25% only partially satisfied. In short, a limited understanding of steps and rights correlates with a high perceived custody risk and a dissatisfaction margin of 15 percentage points over satisfaction, indicating the need for clear, standardized procedures, receipt-based handovers, and straightforward public guidance to rebuild confidence.

Table 7: Economic Hardship & Equity Impacts of Vehicle Seizure

Question	Responses	Percentage/ Perceptions
Financial hardship for citizens?	Somewhat	35%
	Yes, severe hardship	65%
Loss Value of the car in Custody	No	5%
	Maybe	10%
	Yes	85%
Affecting livelihood?	Maybe	20%
	Yes	80%

These results highlight the economic hardship and equity implications of vehicle seizure, particularly for low-income individuals who rely on vehicles for their livelihoods. A large majority, 80%, confirm that vehicle seizure directly affects their livelihood, while 20% state it may affect them. These findings suggest that vehicle seizure not only disrupts income sources

but also leads to long-term economic losses and deepens inequality. For families dependent on their vehicles for work, each day of detention translates into foregone earnings and asset depreciation, compounding hardship. Financial strain is equally evident: 65% of respondents report facing severe hardship, and another 35% experience some financial burden. Furthermore, 85% believe that vehicles lose value while in custody, with 10% saying maybe, and only 5% rejecting this view.

Figure 12: Judiciary Decision

The economic losses stem largely from prolonged judicial decision times in car Supardari cases. The results are a clear public mandate for timely judicial decisions on Supardari. 85% of respondents favor a court time limit of 30 to 60 days for vehicle release decisions, only 10% disagree, and 5% call for an accelerated track within 5 days if the vehicles are used as commercial assets or income-earning vehicles. These preferences signal that delay is not just a procedural issue, but an equity problem that affects lower-income users the most. A statutory decision window, with fast-track triage for income-dependent vehicles, standardized documentation, and receipt-based custody handovers would cut earnings losses, curb depreciation, and strengthen trust in the courts.

Table 8: Public Preferences for Custody Accountability and Compensation Mechanisms in Car Supardari Cases

Question	Responses	Percentage/ Perceptions
Protection Responsibility?	Judiciary	5%
	Government treasury	10%
	Independent body	25%
	Police	60%
digital system to track seized vehicles	Support	15%
	Strongly Support	85%
Govt. Compensation	No	5%
	Yes	95%

Based on these results, there should be a clear custody and accountability regime that the public can see and trust. Since 60 percent assign day-to-day responsibility to police, custody should remain operationally with the police but under an independent oversight body for audits and complaints, reflecting the 25 percent who prefer external supervision and the very low share for the judiciary or treasury. A nationwide digital registry for seized vehicles should be mandated to include unique case IDs, ownership verification, photos at intake and release, condition logs, and chain-of-custody entries. This aligns with 85 percent who strongly support digitization and 15 percent who support it. Time limits for Supardari decisions should be codified, with a standard window of 30 to 60 days and a fast-track for income-earning vehicles. A compensation mechanism should be established because 95 percent of respondents support restitution in the event of damage or misuse during custody.

Figure 13: Perceptions on prolonged custody and timelines for Supardari decisions

The findings are unequivocal: prolonged custody harms seized vehicles and imposes avoidable costs. 80% report financial loss due to damage and depreciation, and the same share favors a firm 30-to-60-day court deadline for Supardari decisions, reflecting a demand for a predictable procedure and asset protection. A small minority prefers an even tighter five-day window or opposes fixed limits, citing the need for case-by-case discretion, especially for income-earning vehicles. Overall, the evidence supports time-bound adjudication, clear SOPs, and higher custodial standards, including condition audits and photo logs. Implementing these steps would safeguard asset value, reduce hardship for owners, and strengthen public trust in the justice system.

4.5. Results and Key Information of the Study

The overall results and discussion describe a system coherent in law but uneven in delivery, and vulnerable to misuse. Lawyers report very high legal literacy regarding constitutional and CrPC safeguards, yet also note low public awareness, inconsistent courtroom practices, and timelines that often slip beyond the nominal one-month window due to file movements, documentation gaps, and scheduling delays. Police and Excise are central to administration and primarily operate under CrPC sections 516-A, 517, and 523. However, their own responses

reveal long impounds, partial or missing digital inventories, irregular maintenance, blurred cost responsibility, and patchy accountability. These operational weaknesses directly map onto the experiences of affected persons: three in four depend on their car for income, most lose a significant share of their earnings during custody, many borrow or sell assets to cope, and an extensive majority report never receiving updates and later notice damage or loss. Several participants alleged that seized vehicles were being used informally by officials or their relatives. Such perceptions fueled misunderstandings and heightened conflict among the affected parties and the authorities. Community views complete the loop—only a quarter fully understand Supardari; about seven in ten perceive frequent or occasional misuse; dissatisfaction outpaces satisfaction; and there is a strong public mandate for 30–60 day court deadlines, independent oversight, digitized custody records, and compensation when damage occurs. Notably, multiple respondents allege a specific pattern of misuse in which smaller seized cars are retained and used personally by officials, a practice that deepens distrust, prolongs detention, and inflates costs for low-income owners. More specifically, the evidence points to a delivery-not-design-gap with a clear equity profile: SOPs and legal anchors exist, but uneven enforcement and weak custody controls convert lawful seizure into prolonged deprivation. Closing the gap requires a unified legal map across CrPC, Motor Vehicle, Excise, and Customs provisions; a single nationwide digital registry with intake/release photos, mileage and GPS logs, and chain-of-custody entries; a codified 30–60 day decision window with a fast-track for income-earning vehicles; clear rules that storage and maintenance costs are borne by the state/custodian—not owners—plus quarterly public reporting, independent audits of custody yards, and meaningful penalties for personal use of seized vehicles, alongside restitution for proven damage or misuse.

4.7. Relevant Case Study

The District and Sessions Judge of Peshawar, Hayat Ali Shah, intervened after repeatedly discovering that investigating officers were violating Section 523 of the Criminal Procedure Code by failing to report seized case property to the courts. Although the law requires police to immediately inform a magistrate and obtain formal orders for the handling or disposal of any seized items, officers routinely bypassed this requirement, often keeping or disposing of property on their own. The judge issued a written directive to the Capital City Police Officer, instructing all investigating officers to report every seizure promptly and to seek court approval before taking any action regarding such property. He also advised magistrates to verify compliance whenever an accused person is brought before them or when an investigation is requested⁵.

5. Conclusion

This study systematically examines the operational realities and obstacles surrounding car Supardari within the framework of Pakistan's case property rights. The primary objective of this study was to examine how existing legal and administrative procedures uphold ownership rights and ensure equitable justice in cases involving vehicles seized during criminal

⁵ <https://www.dawn.com/news/368071/peshawar-police-told-not-to-dispose-of-case-property>

proceedings. To achieve this objective, we used a mixed-method approach design that utilized structured questionnaires from the administrative authorities that are frequently involved in such cases, including the police department, lawyers, and judiciary representatives, aimed to assess how efficiently existing administrative and legal procedures safeguard ownership rights and ensure justice in cases involving seized vehicles. The analysis indicates that, despite the Code of Criminal Procedure, which provides a well-structured legal foundation for Supardari, its implementation remains inconsistent and inefficient. The key identified obstacles include delayed judicial decisions and processes, weak coordination across institutions, and poor maintenance of seized vehicles. These practical shortcomings result in financial losses, erode public trust, and undermine confidence in the Pakistani criminal justice system.

Policy Recommendations

1. Harmonizing Vehicle Supardari under a Unified Legal Framework

Adopt a single, consolidated legal instrument to govern vehicle seizure, custody, and supardari, updating fragmented Cr.P.C. provisions. A harmonized framework with clear definitions, standardized conditions, time-bound decisions, and digital chain-of-custody protocols would eliminate ambiguity, reduce discretionary misuse, and ensure uniform, rights-consistent implementation across all provinces.

2. Standardized Storage and Custody Management for Seized Vehicles

Develop a province-linked system that standardizes how seized vehicles are documented, preserved, and accessed until final disposal. Uniform protocols, digital record-keeping, and transparent custody practices will reduce disputes, protect vehicle condition, and enhance institutional accountability.

3. Centralized District Vehicle Storage Centres

Each district should designate one digitalized storage center—utilizing existing government premises—to consolidate all seized vehicles currently scattered across police stations. Mandatory intake procedures, secure preservation measures, and defined documentation timelines would create an auditable chain of custody and significantly minimize deterioration, tampering, and liability disputes.

4. Instant Ownership Transfer to Prevent Misuse and Wrongful Liability

Vehicle ownership transfer must occur immediately at the time of sale via real-time integration with the excise system, ensuring the seller ceases to hold legal responsibility upon completion of the transaction. In cases involving illegal activity, custody and supardari obligations should apply strictly to the individual apprehended—not to prior owners—thereby preventing wrongful liability and reducing administrative conflict.

5. Integrated Digital Registry & Chain-of-Custody System

Introduce a unified digital registry that generates a QR-coded case ID at seizure and tracks all subsequent steps—storage, inspections, court orders, release, or disposal. The system should maintain an immutable audit trail and provide two interfaces: (i) an official portal for authorized agencies, and (ii) a public, non-personalized dashboard for transparency. Ensuring interoperability and data security will strengthen accountability across the entire process.

6. One-Window Service and Owner Facilitation Mechanism

Implement a unified physical and online one-window service for all seized-vehicle procedures, including status checks, document uploads, bond submissions, appointment scheduling, and retrieval of court orders. Automated notifications, transparent fee structures, standardized conditions for supardari, and a precise grievance-redress mechanism will enhance citizen experience and reduce procedural delays.

7. Time-Bound Seizure Logging and Differentiated Case Handling

A clear and time-bound system should be introduced for vehicle case property. Every seized vehicle should be recorded within 24 hours with photos and VIN, engine, and chassis details. Supardari should be decided within 7–10 court days through a standard format. Owners should be given 14 days' written notice to prove their claim before confiscation starts, and the challan should also be issued within 14 days. The release, confiscation, or disposal of the vehicle should then be completed within 30–50 days. Police must be barred from using detained vehicles, and proper records and oversight should be required to protect property rights.

To prevent unnecessary economic loss, the framework should distinguish clearly between **major** and **minor** offenses.

- **Major cases**—such as murder, terrorism, narcotics, large-scale smuggling, or concealment of prohibited items require **longer custody**, with the vehicle kept under state control until investigation milestones are completed (recommended **30–45 days**, extendable by court order).
- **Minor cases**—traffic violations, documentation lapses, small-value administrative offenses should not trigger long-term seizure. The vehicle should remain with the owner under supardari, with production guaranteed when required. Where appropriate, **finer** should replace physical seizure to avoid vehicle damage, storage costs, and loss of individual income.

Research and Institutional Ownership: National Influencers

National Influencers, a non-partisan and independent public policy think tank based in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, owns and leads this research as part of its broader effort to strengthen evidence-based policy debate in Pakistan. In a society where beliefs often outweigh facts and policy recommendations are sometimes reduced to wish lists, National Influencers seeks to promote clear arguments, effective communication, strategic outreach, and empirically grounded knowledge. The organization aims to contribute to Pakistan's political and intellectual movement by encouraging structural reforms, free enterprise, individual freedom, and equality before the law. In this context, the present research examines the challenges associated with case property management, particularly regarding seized vehicles, and highlights its significance for the protection of property rights in Pakistan. It emphasizes that ensuring timely, transparent, and accountable management and release of case property is not only a legal and administrative issue but also a matter of property security, economic protection, legal recognition, protection from institutional negligence and arbitrary delay, reduction of misuse and weak accountability, human dignity, public trust, and broader economic stability.

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